

GOLD

Growing energy crops on contaminated
land for biofuels and soil remediation

 Ref. Ares(2021)6278601 - 14/10/2021

Dissemination and Communication Plan

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006873.

Document Summary

Deliverable Number: **D4.1**

Version: **1.0**

Due date: 31.08.2021

Actual submission date: 31.082021

Work Package: 4 – Dissemination, communication and international collaboration

Task: 4.1 – Stakeholders mapping, dissemination and communication plan

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Dissemination level: Public

Project Number: **101006873**

Grant Agreement Number: **101006873**

Programme: **GOLD**

Start date of Project: **1st May 2021**

Duration: **48 months**

Project coordinator: **CRES**

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Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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GOLD

Table of contents

Introduction.....	5
1 The pathway to impact.....	6
1.1 GOLD expected impacts.....	7
1.2 Measures to maximize the impact	8
2 Target groups and key messages.....	10
2.1 Implementing key messages	11
2.2 Target groups and stakeholder mapping	12
3 Tools for Communication and Dissemination	13
3.1 Visual Identity	14
3.2 Online Presence.....	14
3.3 Events	16
3.4 Publications.....	17
3.5 Demo and Open Days	17
4 Plan for tasks implementation.....	18
4.1 Time-plan	18
5 GOLD Impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	20
Annex I: Stakeholders Mapping	21

Introduction

The GOLD Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) provides a guideline to promote the project's initiatives, activities and results to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective way.

The strategy contained in this DCP has been developed focusing on the project goals and expected impacts.

The core concept of GOLD is to grow selected high-yielding lignocellulosic energy crops on contaminated lands in order to achieve a double goal: to produce feedstock for clean biofuels with low Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) risk while contributing to land restoration, by applying optimized phytoremediation solutions.

The GOLD Dissemination and Communication Plan sets out the following **specific objectives**:

1. To increase the awareness of the project at EU and global level, by spreading key findings on win-win situations of biofuels production and land decontamination to a wide and diversified audience;
2. To assure high and long-term project visibility beyond the project duration;
3. To increase the awareness on the project's objectives and findings among European and International relevant stakeholders, by engaging them in a continuous and iterative dialogue during the full duration of the project;
4. To facilitate the exploitation of the project's foreground and its uptake at scientific, industrial and policy level.

This deliverable is developed according to the following structure: the identification of target audiences and the scope of their engagement, the formulation of project messages and outputs and the development of tools and actions for the dissemination at scientific level and the communication to a wider audience (regulators, policy-makers, press and media). Online activities will include website management, content creation, social media campaigns, webinars, and publications. Offline activities will include the participation to conferences and clustering/networking meetings and the organization of project events at EU and international level. The dissemination and communication of the project will give strong emphasis on the international collaboration since partners from India, China and Canada are included.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan represents an essential tool to guide the activities of the Consortium throughout the lifetime of the project and beyond. It is conceived as a **living document**, reflecting the developments of the projects and open to any change that may occur; accordingly, it will be updated annually with the contribution of all the partners.

Dissemination and communication of data and results will be performed in compliancy with the IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) rules adopted by the Grant Consortium Agreement.

GOLD

1 The pathway to impact

This DCP outlines the logical steps to promote the project initiatives and impacts since the project outset, with the aim for the GOLD community to achieve impactful results during the project’s lifetime, while laying the groundwork for further outcomes enabling the full deployment of the project’s impacts beyond its end. From an operative point of view, this DCP:

1. makes a balanced use of both traditional tools requiring physical attendance (e.g. physical workshops and gatherings, promotional materials and factsheets in print version, etc.) and digital tools based on web streaming and presence (dedicated web areas, social media, webinars, digital campaigns, videos, etc.);
2. aim at reaching out a very broad audience at EU level as well as promoting international collaboration, specifically with third countries that have partners in the project, namely Canada, China and India. Target audiences will belong to the international scientific community, public representatives and policymakers, industries, NGOs, besides media and citizens.

To accomplish its goals, the GOLD pathway to impact is designed around the three pillars of **Communication**, **Dissemination** and support to **Exploitation**, as defined by the European Commission:

Table 1: the concepts of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation. Re-elaboration from European Commission.

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Objective	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU funded research.	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.
Focus	Inform about and promotion of the project and its results/success.	Focus on results ensuring the results are available for others to use	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)
Target Audience	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community including media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partners, policymakers).	People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.

GOLD

Each one of these three elements have specific objectives and focus and address distinct target audiences. This means that contents and tools must be adjusted to the specific needs, interests and potential for involvement of the target audiences. Although, they should not be conceived as separate sectors, but as integrated dimensions of the overarching strategy to maximise the impact of the project. Accordingly, while the present document is focused on planning and implementing Communication and Dissemination activities, the outcomes achieved through the related measures will pave the way for Exploitation actions as well.

1.1 GOLD expected impacts

The implementation of GOLD will contribute to the objectives of the EU Green Deal, such as zero pollution for a toxic-free environment, preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity, clean affordable and secure energy, to transform the EU economy for a sustainable future. At the same time, the approach and solutions developed by GOLD will support the achievement of several of the Sustainable Development Goals, such as:

SDG2 - Zero hunger: By producing feedstock for biofuels from contaminated land under on-going remediation, useful agricultural land will be released for food and feed production.

SDG3 - Good health and well-being: the innovative phytoremediation strategies and optimised solutions will restore degraded/contaminated land, contributing to reduce the exposure to hazardous chemicals and to contaminated groundwater and soil, bringing benefits in terms of human health.

SDG6 - Clean water and sanitation: the phytoremediation strategies and optimised solutions will reduce leaching of nutrients and pollutants, and will improve the control, transformation, dissipation, and management of organic compounds in soil and groundwater.

SDG7 - Affordable and clean energy: Production of clean fuels from biomass and the use of GOLD innovative conversion technologies will support the increase of the proportion of the population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology.

SDG8 - Decent work and economic growth: The restoration of contaminated soils and the output of biofuel feedstock will create opportunities to increase the number of jobs in crop production, logistics, conversion and distribution of biofuels.

SDG9 - Industry, innovation and infrastructure: GOLD's activities will support the development of innovative entrepreneurship by exploiting the biomass of the energy crop to produce clean biofuels through state-of-the-art processes and technologies.

SDG12 - Responsible production and consumption: Cultivating energy crops in contaminated lands following a low input management will reduce the material and ecological footprint of the produced biomass.

SDG13 - Climate action: The use of harvested biomass for clean biofuel production will support the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

SDG 15 - Life on land: the proposed innovative phytoremediation strategies and optimised solutions will support the restoration of degraded/contaminated lands and soils.

GOLD

Contributing to UN Sustainable Development Goals.

1.2 Measures to maximize the impact

The Communication actions are strategically planned to target multiple audiences including media and the broad public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. They are aimed at:

- Raising awareness and promoting GOLD, its results;
- Showing the impact and the benefits of GOLD as EU-funded project which can deliver solutions to some of the societal challenges targeted by the new EU Green Deal;
- Showing the benefits and the opportunities of International Cooperation for European research and commercial organizations.

Dissemination actions will focus on raising awareness of the main target stakeholders that could potentially uptake and further develop or utilize the project results at scientific, agricultural, business and regulatory level. It will be open access to make the public disclosure of outcomes as widest as possible.

This GOLD Communication and Dissemination Plan is structured according to the following **principles**:

Who	Identify the target groups to address
What	Define clear messages to be conveyed, with a content in line with the profile of the target audience
How	Define and deploy the appropriate tools to convey the messages to the target audience
When	Plan the appropriate time to carry out both communication and dissemination activities, with respect to the project timeline.

GOLD

A periodical monitoring of the effectiveness of the effectiveness of the planned actions and of the overall C&D strategy will be performed at regular times with the aim of ensuring continuous improvement and flexibility to adapt to the specific needs emerging during the project implementation.

Figure 1: D&C principles and monitoring process. Source:European Commission

The Communication activities will be launched since the initial phase of GOLD in order to raise awareness and interest in the project, at first by developing a consistent visual identity for the early-stage communication materials (common templates, slides, social media cards, website etc.). This will be supplemented by outreach activities on the social media, as well as press releases, regular website updates and other actions, to inform a wide public about the project and how it can contribute to societal challenges in a positive way.

The communication activities will last throughout the entire project lifetime but they will be supplemented by dissemination activities such as publications, workshops/webinars and events, as soon as the first projects results will be available, aimed to inform specific targeted audiences of researchers, farmers, policy makers, regulatory bodies, that could uptake the project results.

2 Target groups and key messages

This section aims to provide a framework of target groups and key messages to be delivered, driven by the following questions:

- Who is in the target audience?
- What is the function of the proposed target groups? How do they contribute to the maximisation of impact?
- What is/are the message(s) to be delivered to the target group?

GOLD communication and dissemination activities will consider two main audiences:

1. **Internal audience**, consisting in the consortium partners and Governing bodies, which share internal information and common background;
2. **External audience**: the ensemble of multiple audiences beyond the project's own community. The number and diversity of stakeholders set the challenge of identifying and engaging them effectively; accordingly, most of communication and dissemination effort is spent toward this type of audience.

Since the project's outset, the consortium addressed the topic of finding clear and consistent messages that suit target audiences. The table below, , represents a preliminary framework of possible **target groups and related key messages** reflecting the initial ambitions and interpretations of the partners towards the GOLD project.

Table II: Who-Why-What to disseminate & communicate

Target audience and stakeholders (who)	Why	Main outputs and key messages (what)
Farmers, Farmers unions, Agricultural advisors & professionals	Replicators and potential service providers or producers for growing energy crops in contaminated lands	Agronomic and mechanization factsheets, opportunities of energy crops for phytoremediation
Land restoration & waste management companies (such as METE (participant)	Adopters of phytoremediation solutions	Potential of phytoremediation through energy crops in contaminated land
Environmental management authorities	Create enabling regulatory environment for phytoremediation through energy crops	Environmental and socio-economic aspect of phytoremediation through energy crops; opportunities and long-term benefits for land recovery, biodiversity, climate change mitigation

<p>Scientific community of bioenergy (including ETIP Bioenergy, EERA Bioenergy Europe)</p>	<p>Review and foster scientific and industrial research in soil phytoremediation, extraction of contaminants, two conversion routes.</p>	<p>Results of cultivation trials, results of conversion trials, extraction of contaminants, recovery and use of biostimulants.</p>
<p>Bioenergy industries and platforms</p>	<p>Generate market pull for growing feedstock for advanced biofuels from contaminated land</p>	<p>Potential of growing lignocellulosic energy crops in contaminated land, feedstock quality aspects, environmental service benefits</p>
<p>European Commission Services (CINEA, DG Agri, RTD, Environment, Energy), EU Parliament (Agri, Envi, ITRE committes)</p>	<p>Create enabling EU policy and regulation for the uptake of phytoremediation and sustainable biofuels through energy crops</p>	<p>Environmental and socio-economic aspect of phytoremediation through energy crops; opportunities and long term benefits for land recovery, biodiversity, climate change mitigation</p>
<p>Media & NGOs Associations and citizens concerned about polluted arable lands and interested in feasible solutions for their recovery; readers of both specialized journals and general-interest magazines (i.e. Agriculture, Energy & Fuels, Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery, Biomass and Bioenergy), including online ones (i.e. Euractiv, etc.).</p>	<p>To provide fact-based knowledge on the opportunity of coupling phytoremediation and advanced biofuels</p>	<p>Sustainability of phytoremediation through lignocellulosic energy crops</p>

2.1 Implementing key messages

During the Kick-off meeting (16 June 2021), a **session** was dedicated to discussing the main concepts that the project wants to convey to the target audience, all the positions of the different partners were considered. The following statements represent the first messages that will guide the initial communication activities of the project in the period M1-M18, and if necessary, they will be updated with the periodic update of the present deliverable.

- Turning a problem into an opportunity: GOLD aims to grow lignocellulosic crops on contaminated sites and produce sustainable biofuels;

GOLD

- GOLD helps in bringing contaminated land back to agriculture and to reduce health risks for the local populations;
- Land is GOLD: combining phytoremediation and biofuel production generates value from unused land;
- GOLD promotes international collaboration and the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals

2.2 Target groups and stakeholder mapping

Stakeholders range across countries and several categories, as previously identified in Table II. Additional target audiences were identified by the **Stakeholders mapping**, an exercise performed with the goal to facilitate stakeholder engagement from the very beginning.

The mapping covers key audiences and multipliers as required by GOLD objectives, consisting of members from the international scientific community, policy and decision-makers at EU and International level, large companies and market operators, NGOs, public and specialized media and citizens.

The full list of relevant stakeholders identified by the project mapping is available in **Annex I** of this DCP.

3 Tools for Communication and Dissemination

This section describes the **toolbox** for the GOLD D&C activities, in relation to:

- the messages to be delivered to the target group
- the proposed channels to interact with the target group

Since the boundaries between certain communication and dissemination actions can be blurry or can sometimes overlap, some of the tools or activities can generate both communication and dissemination, depending on the target group and their content.

The table below features the planned communication and dissemination activities in relation to their way of implementation, target audience(s), and expected impacts. Each activity will be then illustrated in detail.

Table III: GOLD D&C activities, audiences, impacts

Activity	Implementation	Audience	Impact
Website	www.GOLD_h2020.eu	Key stakeholders, media, general public	Ensure online presence and visibility and main repository of project outputs
Social media	LinkedIn, Facebook & Twitter	Key stakeholders, media, general public	Ensure active outreach to a wide audience, raise awareness on project scope and results
Webinars	Online webinars open to public	Researchers, students, regulatory bodies,	Dissemination of specific project aspects on phytoremediation, biofuel conversion, value chain optimization, mainly to scientific stakeholders
Videos	1 general introductory video and vide interviews from activities, etc.	All relevant stakeholders	Improve visibility; transfer knowledge
Networking with relevant EU platforms and organisations.	Joint workshops, presentations, direct meetings	Key industry and agriculture stakeholders,	Enlarge the stakeholder's base, liaise and cooperate in joint activities
Open workshops/days	In large exhibitions for agriculture.	Farmers and environmental organizations	Transfer knowledge on improved phytoremediation solutions with energy crops, use of low-input agricultural management in contaminated land
Promotional publications	Leaflets, newsletters, brochures, etc.	Project partners, EC, key stakeholders and general media	Keep the community informed about the project activities and aware of the project's scope and outcomes

GOLD

Demo days	Organized In conjunction with the periodical project meetings	GOLD partners and local stakeholders in the partner countris	Knowledge transfer to the local stakeholders; direct interaction between partners and local audience
Scientific publications	Open access articles in journals, proceedings, books, etc.	Scientific community	Make the scientific results available about phytoremediation, biofuel conversion routes, extraction of contaminants, sustainability assessment
Presentations to conferences, etc.	Participation to scientific conferences	Scientific community	Scientists, companies, etc.
Videos	1 general plus videos from activities, etc.	All relevant stakeholders	Improve visibility; transfer knowledge

3.1 Visual Identity

The whole Communication and Dissemination activity will be marked by the GOLD visual identity made by a project logo with appropriate colour scheme and fonts, so to be clearly recognizable and promptly associated to the project. A specific profile image was developed for GOLD website and social channels.

All the partners will be provided with the project logo and other early-stage C&D material, which includes: general project presentation, templates for documents, slides and poster, rollup for presentations and displaying at events. Other materials include a project brochure and a leaflet.

By the time of preparation of this deliverable the official project logo and visual identity of the project have already been designed and adopted. These materials are extensively presented in **D4.2 – Dissemination and Communication toolkit**. Updates of the kit will be provided during the project in line with the emerging needs of the Consortium.

3.2 Online Presence

The online presence of GOLD project will be mainly based on the project official website, different social channels, and promotional online publications such as an e-newsletter.

The website will act as a main reference point to promote the visibility of the project and its results. The website is available at the URL <https://www.gold-h2020.eu/>. Different webpages are dedicated to present detailed information on the project's background, partners, activities, resources (including deliverables and

publications), international cooperation and events, as well as the open access tool with the stakeholders mapping and projections of the project. A news section will also be included and frequently updated.

Figure 5: GOLD website homepage. <https://www.gold-h2020.eu/>.

Social media channels will constitute an important tool to connect to and engage with different types of audience, and to drive traffic to the website. The following project pages and profiles were created:

Table IV: GOLD social media presence

Social media channel: name and URL	Target audience to be engaged
Twitter: GOLD Project H2020 @gold_h2020 https://twitter.com/gold_h2020	More general audience, press and policymakers
Facebook: GOLD Project H2020 https://www.facebook.com/GOLD-Project-H2020-110487614638871	
LinkedIn: GOLD Project H2020 https://www.linkedin.com/company/gold-project-h2020/	Business, policy and scientific stakeholders

GOLD

Other social channels that may be integrated are: **Youtube** (for posting videos, interviews etc.) and **Research Gate** (to share publications and engage more prominently scientific audience).

In order to deliver the content to a wide audience, these accounts will be crosslinked among them, and connections will be established and kept with other channels and accounts: the social media of the consortium organizations, other EU projects on similar themes, official accounts of EU institutions and of international collaborations on a global level, such as @EUSciencehub, @Inea, @ETIPBioenergy, @MissionInnovation, @@Biofutureplatform, as well as with other similar EU projects financed by the same Horizon 2020 call such as @phy2climate.

Hashtags will be mentioned, such as: #H2020; #HorizonEU; #EUclimateaction; #climatechange; #renewablefuels; #phytomanagement #greentransition; #ResearchImpactEU; #EUresearch; #innovation; #sustainableenergy; #EUGREENWEEK; #EUGreenDeal; etc.

This list will be periodically updated by checking the overview of social media accounts with EU input and the online EU events calendar.

At consortium level, each partner will ensure the promotion of the project tweets, newsletters and posts to its own list of relevant media contacts.

A project **e-newsletter** will be published every six months (8 in total) and sent to subscribers on the project website, in compliance with the GDPR. It will be also shared through both the project's channels and the partner organizations channels.

3.3 Events

Info-sessions. A series of 2-3 project info-sessions (half-day or shorter) and presentations will be organized on the occasion of relevant biomass, agriculture and environmental science conferences (i.e., Ecomondo Circular Economy Expo etc., European Biomass Conference and Exhibition and others). A dedicated info-session will be organized in the framework of **Mission Innovation events** dedicated to sustainable biofuels (i.e the International Conference on Sustainable Biofuels).

One international **interim event** will be held as a side event of the **EUBCE – European Biomass Conference and Exhibition** in order to present the status, and the preliminary results of the project as well as to collect feedback from peers. On this occasion, the Consortium will seek opportunities for co-organization and synergies with similar EU projects and networking/interaction with European initiatives and platforms (i.e ETIP Bioenergy, EERA Bioenergy).

One **final conference** (one day) will be organized in Brussels to present the results to a wide audience of stakeholders. A track of the event will focus on the role of EU-International cooperation and opportunities in phytoremediation for sustainable biofuels globally.

At least three **webinars** will complement physical events:

- *Webinar 1* will be focused on the agronomic/environmental aspects of phytoremediation with lignocellulosic crops;
- *Webinar 2* will be focused more on the aspects of conversion processes into advanced biofuels, the separation and management of contaminants from the feedstock/product;
- *Webinar 3* will be dedicated to International Collaboration. Partners, peers and representatives of countries members of Mission Innovation Challenge 4 will be invited to present the results of their

GOLD

respective activities in specific sessions, and to participate in a dedicated moderated discussion on the opportunities of International Collaboration for phytoremediation and sustainable biofuels.

All the webinars will be public, and the recordings will be available on the project's website. Additional webinars may be organized in case of further needs from the Consortium or in case of difficulties to travel internationally due to *force majeure*.

3.4 Publications

Press releases. At least three project press releases will be published, one at the beginning of the project after the kick-off meeting (already available on the project's [website](#)), one at the interim (M24) and one before or in combination with the final event (M48).

Factsheets and policy briefs will be produced for all the main deliverables of the project.

Outreach articles. At least three outreach articles will be published in relevant international and national magazines. In addition, all project partners will be involved in this task and will contribute to writing articles and updates for national magazines and media in order to ensure dissemination at their respective country level.

Scientific publications will be **open access**, in compliance with the Horizon 2020 Open Access¹ policy; the whole publication activity will be organized by the Project Editorial Board.

A final **project booklet** (provisional title: "*Phytoremediation and advanced biofuels with lignocellulosic crops*") will be edited by ETA, published digitally and printed for distribution at the final event. The booklet will focus on the results and the impact of the project, with an indication of the way forward for the further scientific, industrial and policy-uptake of phytoremediation from lignocellulosic crops, so to constitute also a legacy and a useful reference of the project after its end. All WP leaders will contribute a section dedicated to the aspects of International Cooperation will be also included.

The recent European Commission tools to support dissemination and exploitation will be also used for the promotion of the project and its results, including [Horizon Dashboard](#), [Horizon Results Platform](#), [Horizon Dashboard](#).

3.5 Demo and Open Days

Demo days will be organised by ETA and CRES in conjunction with the technical meetings of the project: there, the partners will have the opportunity to visit both pilot field trials (combined if possible with harvesting events) and laboratory facilities on conversion technologies. At least four meetings will be combined with demo days while interviews will be made to the partners to be used in the project's videos.

Moreover, at least three **open days** will be organized to increase project visibility preferable as side events to exhibitions.

¹H2020 Funding Guide: Open Access https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

4 Plan for tasks implementation

4.1 Time-plan

During the first year the main activities will be targeted at raising the awareness and interest about the project among a wide audience of stakeholders and disseminating the results from the first deliverables of the project. These activities will include an initial press release, the sharing of project digital flyers, the establishment of the online presence: website design, setup and regular update with content creation, update of the social media channels. These tools will be maintained and used throughout the lifetime of the project.

Gradually, an increasing number of events will take place: the Info-sessions will start at the early stage (between M1 and M24), then a series of webinars will follow, and in Year 3 a major interim event will be held at the annual EUBCE – European Biomass Conference. Finally, a Brokerage event will celebrate the project closure, being a major opportunity to present the achieved results to a broad audience. Main events will be followed by a dedicated press release.

The following Gantt chart outlines the main communication and dissemination activities planned for the period M1-M18. This can be subject to modifications and updates depending on the needs emerging during the implementation of the project, and will be updated at M18 with the update of the present deliverable.

GOLD

Project Kickoff
June 16, 2021

5 GOLD Impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Measurable control points and periodic assessments will be performed at consortium level (at least every 6 months). Specific **Impact Key Performance Indicators (IKPIs)** will be used to monitor the performance of WP4, including:

- Website: number of users accessing and sessions opened
- Social media channels: number of followers, views and interactions
- Events: number of attendants, number of events attended by GOLD partners
- Publications: number of published pieces, citation, accesses, download etc.

References

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Annex I: Stakeholders Mapping

The Stakeholders Mapping was performed in the early months of the project, and it succeeded in identifying **48 specific relevant stakeholders**. Most of them have directly expressed their interest in the project with letters of Support and Commitment, while other ones were detected with the contribution of all the Consortium partners.

The identified stakeholders are listed below by country, with details about their field of activity that is relevant for GOLD objectives (when available). In compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679, the contact information of these stakeholders is stored in a separate file, which is kept confidential.

	Name and Field of Activity (relevant for GOLD)	Country
1	Mission Innovation, Mission Innovation is a global initiative catalysing action and investment in research, development and demonstration to make clean energy affordable, attractive and accessible for all.	Global
2	European Commission Services, DG RTD, DG ENER, DG AGRI, DG RTD	Belgium
3	Plants for the Future European Technology Platform, a stakeholder forum for the plant sector with members from industry, academia and the farming community.	Belgium
4	European Technology and Innovation Platform Bioenergy ETIP Bioenergy is an industry-led stakeholder platform that brings together relevant actors from academia, industry, and civil society, engaged in the development of sustainable bioenergy and competitive biofuel technologies.	Germany
5	CERESIS Project Contaminated land Remediation through Energy crops for Soil improvement to liquid biofuel Strategies. H2020 project funded by the same call as GOLD LC-SC3-RES-37-2020	Greece
6	Phy2Climate A double-aimed innovative scheme enables the full exploitation of contaminated land for sustainable biofuel production. H2020 project funded by the same call as GOLD LC-SC3-RES-37-2020	Austria
7	University of Melbourne, School of Biosciences, International authority on eco-physiological aspects of the impact of heavy metals pollution on plants and pioneer on the establishment of phytoremediation technology for soils decontamination.	Australia
8	CNPEM/LNBR, Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials - Brazilian Biorenewables National Laboratory	Brazil
9	Georgia Tech Institute, Expertise in the areas of environmental biotechnology and bioprocess engineering for the bioremediation of contaminated natural systems.	USA

10	IINAS, International Institute for Sustainability Analysis and Strategy	Germany
11	SEI, Stockholm Environment Institute International – Africa Research and Energy and Climate Change Programme	Kenya
12	AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, MBA Food & Agribusiness	Greece
13	Enerkem Inc., Active company on biofuels (methanol and ethanol) under the general concept of the circular economy and following the bio-refinery concept.	Canada
14	Fertil'Innov Environnement, A young Innovative Company implementing ecological engineering strategies to the sustainable development of soil microorganisms.	France
15	Agroapps PC, A company dedicated to providing sustainable solutions that help modern farming and agriculture, while using state-of-the-art innovative IT technologies (energy crops and soil management included).	Greece
16	General Director Care of the Environment Territory Emilia Romagna, Governmental body	Italy
17	HELACTOR, Company with several activities, among others, on renewable energy sources and sustainability	Greece
18	City Rusa Slaska, Local authority in Poland	Poland
19	HELLABIOM, Hellenic Biomass Association	Greece
20	TEREO, company offering services on polluted sites and soils, studies and depollution of soils and groundwater	France
21	BIOS AGROSYSTEMS, Large company pioneer in the area of energy crops for biofuel production	Greece
22	WFOSIGW, Regional Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Lublin	Poland
23	ILEIA Prefecture, Municipality of Andravida-Killini which is located in south Greece (Peloponnesus)	Greece
24	HUNAN Guli New Energy Technology Co. Ltd, Part of Chinese Government Industry, Clean biofuels production	China
25	Anxiang Hauchung New Energy Technology Co., Ltd Company with expertise in Phytoremediation and Clean biofuels production	China
26	Hunan Airbluer Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd Company with expertise in Phytoremediation	China

27	AGRIOPALE SERVICES, A company producing bioenergy	France
28	Communauté d'Agglomération Hénin-Carvin, Location of GOLD pilot fields	France
29	FAO, GBEP - Global Bioenergy Partnership	Italy
30	TBM Europe BV, Biomass Energy Solution	Netherlands
31	SRTA-City, City of Scientific Research and Technological Applications	Egypt
32	IBC- Institute of Bioenergy Crops has long-term experience on growing energy crops like switchgrass on contaminated lands	Ukraine
33	ARTISANS Technologies, company	India
34	EUBIA, European Biomass Industrial Association	EU (Brussels)
35	Municipality of Kozani, Location of establishment CRES pilot fields	Greece
36	Sociedade Agricola do Golaio, Cabeco de Verdo	Portugal
37	PRELIS LTD	Portugal
38	Canna Casa, SME working on industrial hemp	Portugal
39	CMC BIOMASS, Company caring for a sustainable world	Portugal
40	CVR, Center for Waste Valorization	Portugal
41	ADEME, French Agency for the Ecological Transition	France
42	CHAMBRE D'AGRICULTURE HAUTS-DE-FRANCE	France
43	UdeS, University of Sherbrook	Canada
44	Prefecture of Western Macedonia, Location of CRES pilot fields	Greece
45	NextGen Ltd, company	India
46	Sign-age PVT Ltd, company	India
47	Path-Breakers, India women organisation	India

48	Jaworzna, Local authority where the trials of UMCS will be located	Poland
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